
ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN MUSIC OF VISAYAS STATE UNIVERSITY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

In order to enhance music education courses, the study's primary goal is to evaluate students' academic performance in music at Visayas State University (VSU). It specifically sought to establish the respondents' age, gender, educational attainment, and demographic profile. It also aimed to determine the students' academic success in music and provide suggestions to enhance the curriculum at the Visayas State University. In the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, the students dominate the younger generation wherein they belong to the age bracket of 16-20 years old. 75% of the participants were females, which reflected the majority of the population. Most of the students only got average grades. The weak background and foundation are due to less time given to music in MAPEH as a subject. Thus, they just encountered proper music education upon reaching the tertiary level hence, lacking the basic skills necessary for them to learn and appreciate the course then and obtain higher grades.

Keywords: academic achievement, music education, students' achievement, analysis, curricular offerings

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INTRODUCTION

Improving instruction to promote efficient and effective student achievement in music is one of the primary concerns of every educational institution. Many governments and international organizations, particularly in poor nations, are becoming more and more interested in understanding how to improve learning outcomes and maximize the return on education spending. A career in music education may be both rewarding and stressful. There is no better way to share one's expertise and enthusiasm as a professional music instructor than to do so if one likes making music and working with others. (NAMM Foundation Supporting Music Education: Choose to Teach 2008). Through music study, students learn the value of sustained effort to achieve excellence and the concrete rewards of hard work resulting in teamwork skills and discipline in line with Edmond's findings, it can be added that an effective school has an indirect effect, on school climate, that stimulates ideas and facilitates the exchange of ideas leads to student achievements.

Researchers have even attempted to explain how IQ, personality, socioeconomic background, and the favorable correlations between musical ability, reading comprehension, and math or art education relate to students' successes.

In line with Stumm, et. According to al. (2011), individual variations in academic achievement have been linked to differences in intellect and personality, particularly for students with higher mental capacity as indicated by I.Q. Higher conscientiousness, which is correlated with a desire for work and success, and rapid learners are more likely to do well on academic tests.

In the field of art education, according to Gardiner (1996), there is mounting evidence that arts education may greatly improve pupils' academic performance. His research provided compelling evidence that sequential, skill-building arts and music teaching linked with the rest of the curriculum may significantly raise students' reading and arithmetic test scores.

Magnuson (2007) noted that the socioeconomic position of parents, which may in some way also affect children's linguistic and social skill development, may have an impact on academic socialization. In these areas, being prepared for school aids children in adjusting to their academic experiences. Tomporowski et al (2008) found that exercise increases neurotic activity in the brain, which improves executive abilities such as attention span and working memory.

Lamar (1993) discovered a strong correlation between musical talent and reading as a successful method of math learning. The same research by Johnson, 2000 showed that musical ability was strongly correlated with academic accomplishment in kids aged eight to twelve. On the other hand, Palos & Tuley's 2003 study found a substantial positive association between academic achievement and the degree of interest in the visual arts.

The school influences students' academic performance, but Kwesiga (2002) contends that school facilities determine the quality of the institution, which in turn influences the students' achievements and attainment. Sentamu (2003) also agreed that a person's choice of school has an impact on their academic achievement since schools have an impact on how the material is arranged as well as how students are taught, learned, and assessed. In theory, all these academics agree that schools impact students' academic achievement.

Legislators and other decision-makers in education must be persuaded of the need of include music in the general curriculum. Music instruction helps students learn more in the classroom, according to supporters of the arts in education. Most writers and public speakers announce their belief in the efficiency of the arts curriculum. This conviction has arisen from personal observations that music students are usually successful in academic achievement. Classroom teachers observed that when music is added to a lesson, students' retention to the lesson is more than that of the lesson that hadn't been integrated with music. These observations have been made by the author as well during 20 years of teaching students in grades K-8. Such observations have led to the development of education research into the question of whether or not what is being observed can be measured and reported. Music education advocates now that it must bring the

information developed from this work to the attention of legislators and other school policy makers to convince them of the value of music in the curriculum.

According to Horne (2005), music instruction enhances possibilities for academic success. High school music students have been shown to hold a higher-grade point average (GPA) than non-musicians at Viejo High School in California USA. It should be emphasized that certain abilities must be present and have grown over the course of previous years in order to pass an audition to join a high school performing arts program. These developmental abilities should ideally be learned in elementary school. According to a 1981 poll, 40% of Westinghouse Science Talent Search winners were talented musicians (California State Dept. of Education, 1986).

Learning to play an instrument hastens students' mental, emotional, physical, and social development. In the studies, it was claimed that playing an instrument would increase one's coordination, focus, and memory, as well as one's vision and hearing function. In summary, the conclusion that musical training refines the growth of the brain and the overall neuromuscular system. The results of this conference have inspired music supporters to fund further investigations into the relationship between music education and brain development.

RESEARCH METHOD

The descriptive research approach was employed for this study, which focuses on the relationships between variables, the testing of hypotheses, and the creation of universally applicable generalizations, principles, or theories (Best and Kahn, 1988). This descriptive research method deals to predict the students' academic achievement in music of VSU as a basis for the improvement in music education course. This type of method was applied by the researcher since the study used frequencies, averages, means and other statistical calculations.

Research Design

The assertions made by the authors about the research's design—whether it was qualitative, quantitative, or a combination of the three—are included in this paragraph. Every strategy provides different research designs for different research ideas. Other approaches are provided by qualitative and mixed methodologies. The section concerning techniques need to include this portion. As a result, it also gives a succinct explanation of the study's variables.

Population and Sample or Subject*

The respondents of the study were BSED-MAPEH students taking up music classes at the Visayas State University and its external campus. There were fifty-six (56) 2nd year BSED-MAPEH students taking up music education classes with a total of sixty-four (64) respondents. The three administrators were taken as the respondents that implements leadership practices and handles, as well as evaluate the school teachers and students. Teacher respondents were teaching music education subjects. The second year BSED MAPEH students were taken as respondents on their academic achievement.

Table 1. Respondents of the study

Campus	Students		TOTAL	
	No.	%	No.	%
VSU - Main	30	46.87	30	46.87
VSU - Tolosa	13	20.31	13	20.31
VSU - Isabel	13	20.31	13	20.31
Total no. of respondents	56	87.49	56	87.49

Table 1.1 shows the distribution of respondents from each of the VSU campuses where eighty-seven-point nine percent (87.9%).

Instruments

The research instrument used in this study was a questionnaire devised by the researcher himself. The self-made survey questionnaire was made for music students.

Table 2. Age distribution of the respondents

Respondents	Age Bracket	Count	Percentage
Students	31-35	1	1.56
	26-30	0	0
	21-35	10	15.62
	16-20	45	70.31
Total		64	100

To improve any variance to student academic achievement these were rated based on the corresponding scale with the use of Likert Scale of 1 – 5, wherein, the following adjectival interpretation was used:

Table 3. Adjectival interpretation Likert Scale

Weighted Mean	Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Most Implemented
3.51 – 4.50	Highly Implemented
2.51 – 3.50	Moderately Implemented
1.51 – 2.50	Partly Implemented
0.00 – 1.50	Not Implemented

Prior to data gathering, the instrument (questionnaires) was pre-tested with fifteen (15) 4th year MAPEH students who already took music classes. This was also done to ensure the clarity of the questions as reflected in the instrument.

Data Analysis

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 4. Age of Respondents

Respondents	Age bracket	No.	%
Students	31-35	1	1.56
	26-30	0	0
	21-25	10	15.62
	16-20	45	70.31
TOTAL		64	100

Table 4 shows the three respondents' age bracket; the students comprising most of the respondent's population belongs to the age bracket of 16-20, 21-25 and 31-35. This indicates that the population is mostly comprised of students who are on their right age when they are enrolled in the tertiary level.

Table 5. Gender of the Respondents

Campus	Gender	Students	Percentage
VSU Main	Male	7	10.93
	Female	23	35.93
VSU-Tolosa	Male	3	4.68
	Female	10	15.62
VSU-Isabel	Male	5	7.81
	Female	8	12.50
Total No. of Respondents	Male	15	23.43
	Female	41	64.06

Table 5 shows that most of the respondents are comprised of females from all three sites namely; 1) VSU-Main with 40.62% of female respondents while, 2) VSU-Tolosa comes in with 18.75%, and, 3) VSU-Isabel with 15.62% having a grand total of 75% of the population, while the male gender of the three sites is only comprised 25% of the entire population.

Table 6. Respondents Educational Attainment

ITEMS	No. of Respondents	Percentage
College Undergrad	56	87.5
TOTAL	56	87.5

Table 6 shows the educational attainment of the respondents; where eighty-seven-point five percent (87.5%) were undergraduate students. It indicates that the population of the respondents are mainly comprised of students taking up music education.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Research Findings

Table 7. Students' Academic Achievement in Music

GRADES	VSU Main	%	VSU Tolosa	%	VSU Isabel	%	TOTAL	%
1.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1.25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1.50	4	7.14	1	1.78	1	1.78	6	10.71
1.75	3	5.35	6	10.71	6	10.71	15	26.78
2.00	7	12.5	2	3.57	4	7.14	13	23.21
2.25	8	14.28	3	5.35	2	3.57	13	23.21
2.50	5	8.92	0	0	0	0	5	8.92
2.75	3	5.35	1	1.78	0	0	4	7.14
3.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	30	46.87	13	20.31	13	20.31	56	100

Table 7 shows the distribution of students grades in music based on teachers rating where twenty-six-point seventy eight percent (26.78%) of the students got a grade of 1.75- and twenty-three-point twenty one percent (23.21%) of the students got a grade of 2.0 and 2.25- and ten-point seventy one percent (10.71%) got a grade of 1.50. It indicates that students taking music education courses were on the average level. They just encountered proper music education upon reaching tertiary level; thus, they lack the basic skills necessary for them to learn and appreciate the course and then obtain higher grades.

Discussion

In order to enhance music education courses, the study's primary goal is to evaluate students' academic performance in music at Visayas State University (VSU). It specifically sought to establish the respondents' age, gender, educational attainment, and demographic profile. It also aimed to determine the students' academic success in music and provide suggestions to enhance the curriculum at the Visayas State University. This study is focused on music students' areas of performance evaluation. Variance of the student academic achievement were rated based on the corresponding scale with the use of Likert scale of 1-5 scale. The data gathered were tabulated and analyzed with the use of Statistical Package for Social Services (SPSS) 16.0 version. To define the sociodemographic features of the respondents, the data were examined using descriptive statistics, which comprise percentages, means, and standard deviation. To determine the reliability of the scales of the itemized instrument (survey questionnaire) Cronbacks Alpha

was used to compute. One-way ANOVA was used to teaching performance of music teachers to students' level of academic achievement.

The demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age the students dominate the younger generation wherein they belong to the age bracket of 16-20 years old. 75% of the participants were females, which reflected the majority of the population. Most of the students only got average grades. From all the groups it was the administrators which were all females. While males were only 25% of the total population. The educational attainment, most of the respondents are college under graduating students since they are just students taking up foundations in music.

Students taking music education course, finds it difficult to obtain higher grades since as they go higher year level, the skills required becomes demanding. Most of the students don't have the skills and proper music education background when they enrolled in music education courses in college. Thus, they just encountered proper music education upon reaching tertiary level thus; they lack the basic skills necessary for them to learn and appreciate the course then obtain higher grades

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were derived. Only average results were obtained by the majority of students. The weak background and foundation are due to less time given to music in MAPEH as a subject. Thus, they just encountered proper music education upon reaching tertiary level hence, they lack the basic skills necessary for them to learn and appreciate the course then obtain higher grades.

The following recommendations are made:

1. It is suggested that there should be screening in the incoming students who will choose to major in MAPEH to assess their musical abilities and level of comprehension towards music education.
2. Teaching staff should be carefully planned and always be put to consideration the age gap between the junior and senior teachers. Mentoring is one of the key factors for the program to work so more junior staff should be given an opportunity to be trained to handle simple administrative jobs, with this, junior faculty should pursue their graduate studies program.

Music education should be given more importance as subject and thus strengthening it further the work of VSU but as well as other Higher Educational Institutions (HEI's) and the Department of Education. Music develops not just knowledge-based learning but it enriches the student's holistic development.

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